

POLICY BRIEF

ADVANCING SUSTAINABLE AND COMPETITIVE AQUACULTURE IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

Insights from multi-stakeholder consultations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Aquaculture plays a vital role in ensuring Europe’s food security, economic resilience, and environmental sustainability. Recent stakeholder discussions have highlighted both opportunities and challenges arising from technological innovation, regulatory complexity, and market dynamics. This policy brief summarizes key findings and proposes policy directions to support a modern, competitive, and sustainable aquaculture sector aligned with the EU Green Deal and Farm-to-Fork Strategy.

1. FEED INNOVATION, CERTIFICATION, AND VALUE CREATION

Functional and sustainable feeds are a key driver of innovation in European aquaculture. By enhancing fish health, nutritional value, and environmental performance, these feeds can contribute to greater food safety and consumer trust. Yet, the introduction of new feed ingredients, additives, and supplements is often constrained by complex and time-consuming approval procedures. At the same time, certification and labelling systems, while essential for ensuring transparency, can increase production costs and limit the accessibility of “premium” products for both producers and consumers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Establish an accessible regulatory framework that promotes and simplifies the approval of novel feed ingredients, additives, and supplements.
- Strengthen traceability and certification systems that verify feed origin, safety, sustainability, and animal welfare to build consumer confidence and reinforce market credibility.
- Promote the value and market development of certified functional feed and sustainable fish, fostering consumer awareness and fair returns for producers.

2. MARKET FAIRNESS AND CONSUMER TRUST

High animal welfare standards enhance product nutritional quality and ensure food safety, while strengthening consumer trust, supporting sustainable and responsible aquaculture in Europe. Compliance with animal welfare regulations imposes significant costs on European producers, while imports from countries with lower welfare standards can undercut prices, creating unfair competition. This disparity threatens the viability of domestic producers and discourages investment in high-welfare practices. The sector also faces increasing challenges from misinformation and “greenwashing,” where sustainability practices are claimed without evidence, undermining consumer confidence and creating a disadvantage for genuinely responsible producers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Create a distinct market segment for “premium” aquaculture products supported by the high standards in European aquaculture.

- Implement a quality certification system based on product history, including a welfare and a sustainability label indicating origin, traceability, and production type. Such certification enhances product value and informs consumers and producers about “premium” aquaculture products. These certifications would promote fair competition and could contribute to better product acceptance and improved consumer trust, particularly if complemented with traceability tools.

3. REGULATORY BARRIERS

Expanding the diversity of the species produced in European aquaculture and introducing new products can enhance sector resilience, through market differentiation in a competitive global market. While the European aquaculture sector faces unfair competition from low-cost imports, limited range of domestically produced species reduces market resilience and constrains competitiveness.

RECOMMENDATION

- Support diversification of aquaculture species and the introduction of new products to strengthen market resilience, expand consumer choice, and overcome unfair competition from lower-cost imports.

4. TECHNOLOGICAL MODERNIZATION AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Harmonizing technologies in aquaculture offers a major opportunity to strengthen food security. Integrating traceability systems based on sensors, Artificial Intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and the Internet of Things (IoT) enables real-time monitoring across production stages, improving transparency, sanitary control, and rapid response to incidents. However, the regulatory framework for AI use in aquaculture remains unclear, creating uncertainty for producers and developers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Establish clear EU guidelines for AI use in aquaculture, ensuring transparency and accountability.
- Promote open and interoperable data systems that balance innovation with data protection.
- Support digital literacy and adoption of smart technologies across the sector.

CONCLUSION

Strengthening Europe’s aquaculture sector calls for coherent policies that foster innovation, ensure fair competition, and enhance consumer trust. Streamlined regulation, clearer guidance on digital technologies, and support for diversification of species can drive competitiveness and sustainability. Combined with robust certification and labelling, these measures will reinforce the sector’s contribution to the EU Green Deal and Farm-to-Fork Strategies, positioning European aquaculture at the forefront of the global transition towards more sustainable and resilient food systems.

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